

GridFTP: A Secure, Efficient Data Transport Mechanism

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Abstract – An emerging class of data-intensive applications involve the geographically dispersed extraction of complex scientific information from very large collections of measured or computed data. Such applications arise, for example, in experimental physics, where the data in question is generated by accelerators, and in simulation science, where the data is generated by supercomputers. So-called Data Grids provide essential infrastructure for such applications, much as the Internet provides essential services for applications such as e-mail and the Web. We describe here service that we believe are fundamental to any Data Grid: reliable, high-speed transport. Our high-speed transport service, GridFTP, extends the popular FTP protocol with new features required for Data Grid applications, such as striping and partial file access. We present the design of this service and also preliminary performance results. Our implementations exploit security and other services provided by the Globus Toolkit.

Keyword- Data Grid, GridFTP, DPSS, HPSS, SRB

INTRODUCTION

The applications that we consider use a variety of storage systems, each designed to satisfy specific needs and requirements for storing, transferring and accessing large datasets. These include the Distributed Parallel Storage System (DPSS) and the High Performance Storage System (HPSS), which provide high-performance access to data and utilize parallel data transfer and/or striping across multiple servers to improve performance [2][3], and the Storage Resource Broker (SRB), which connects heterogeneous data collections, provides a uniform client interface to storage repositories, and provides a metadata catalog for describing and locating data within the storage system [4].

Unfortunately, these storage systems typically use incompatible and often unpublished protocols for accessing data, and therefore each requires the use of its own client. These incompatible protocols and client libraries effectively partition the datasets available on the Grid. Applications that require access to data stored in different storage systems must use multiple access methods.

To overcome these incompatible protocols, we propose a universal Grid data transfer and

access protocol called GridFTP that provides secure, efficient data movement in Grid environments. This protocol, which extends the standard FTP protocol, provides a superset of the features offered by the various Grid storage systems currently in use. We argue that using GridFTP as a common data access protocol would be mutually advantageous to Grid storage providers and users. Storage providers gain a broader user base, because their data are available to any client, while storage users gain access to a broader range of storage systems and data.

We chose to extend the FTP protocol (rather than, for example, WebDAV) because we observed that FTP is the protocol most commonly used for data transfer on the Internet and the most likely candidate for meeting the Grid's needs. FTP is a widely implemented and well-understood IETF standard protocol with a large base of code and expertise from which to build. In addition, the FTP protocol provides a well-defined architecture for protocol extensions and supports dynamic discovery of the extensions supported by a particular implementation. Third, numerous groups have added extensions through the IETF, and some of

these extensions are particularly useful in the Grid.

THE GLOBUS TOOLKIT

The term Grid computing refers to the merging computational and networking infrastructure that is designed to provide pervasive, uniform and reliable access to data, computational, and human resources distributed over wide area environments [1]. Grid services allow scientists at locations throughout the world to share data collection instruments such as particle colliders, compute resources such as supercomputers and clusters of workstations, and community datasets stored on network caches and hierarchical storage systems. The Globus Toolkit developed within the Globus project provides middleware services for Grid computing environments. Major components include the Grid Security Infrastructure (GSI), which provides public-key-based authentication and authorization services; resource management services, which provide a language for specifying application requirements, mechanisms for immediate and advance reservations of Grid resources, and for remote job management; and information services, which provide for the distributed publication and retrieval of information about Grid resources. Data Grid services complement and build on these components. For example, the GridFTP transfer service and the replica management service described in the rest of this paper use GSI for authentication and authorization. Higher-level data replication services can use the information service to locate the “best” replica and the resource management service to reserve the computational, network, and storage resources required by a data movement operation.

GRIDFTP FUNCTIONALITY

GridFTP functionality includes some features that are supported by FTP extensions that have already been standardized (RFC 959) but are seldom implemented in current systems. Other features are new extensions to FTP.

Grid Security Infrastructure and Kerberos support:

Robust and flexible authentication, integrity, and confidentiality features are critical when transferring or accessing files. GridFTP must support GSI and Kerberos authentication, with user controlled setting of various levels of data integrity and/or confidentiality. GridFTP implements the authentication mechanisms

defined by RFC 2228, “FTP Security Extensions”.

Third-party control of data transfer:

To manage large datasets for distributed communities, we must provide authenticated third-party control of data transfers between storage servers. A third-party operation allows a user or application at one site to initiate, monitor and control a data transfer operation between two other sites: the source and destination for the data transfer. Our implementation adds Generic Security Services (GSS)-API authentication to the existing third-party transfer capability defined in the FTP standard.

Parallel data transfer:

On wide-area links, using multiple TCP streams in parallel (even between the same source and destination) can improve aggregate bandwidth over using a single TCP stream [5]. GridFTP supports parallel data transfer through FTP command extensions and data channel extensions.

Striped data transfer:

Data may be striped or interleaved across multiple servers, as in a DPSS network disk cache [6]. GridFTP includes extensions that initiate striped transfers, which use multiple TCP streams to transfer data that is partitioned among multiple servers. Striped transfers provide further bandwidth improvements over those achieved with parallel transfers. We have defined GridFTP protocol extensions that support striped data transfers.

Partial file transfer:

Some applications can benefit from transferring portions of files rather than complete files: for example, high-energy physics analyses that require access to relatively small subsets of massive, object-oriented physics database files. The best that the standard FTP protocol allows is transfer of the remainder of a file starting at a particular offset. GridFTP provides commands to support transfers of arbitrary subsets or regions of a file.

Automatic negotiation of TCP buffer/window sizes:

Using optimal settings for TCP buffer/window sizes can dramatically improve data transfer performance. However, manually setting TCP buffer/window sizes is an error-prone process (particularly for non-experts) and is often simply

not done. GridFTP extends the standard FTP command set and data channel protocol to support both manual setting and automatic negotiation of TCP buffer sizes for large files and for large sets of small files.

Support for reliable and restartable data transfer:

Reliable transfer is important for many applications that manage data. Fault recovery methods are needed to handle failures such as transient network and server outages. The FTP standard includes basic features for restarting failed transfers that are not widely implemented. GridFTP exploits these features and extends them to cover the new data channel protocol.

THE GRIDFTP PROTOCOL IMPLEMENTATION

Our implementation of the GridFTP protocol supports partial file transfers, third-party transfers, parallel transfers and striped transfers. We do not yet support automatic negotiation of TCP buffer/window sizes. The implementation consists of two principal C libraries: the `globus_ftp_control_library` and the `globus_ftp_client_library`.

The `globus_ftp_control_library` implements the control channel API. This API provides routines for managing a GridFTP connection, including authentication, creation of control and data channels, and reading and writing data over data channels. Having separate control and data channels, as defined in the FTP protocol standard, greatly facilitates the support of such features as parallel, striped and third-party data transfers. For parallel and striped transfers, the control channel is used to specify a put or get operation; concurrent data transfer occurs over multiple parallel TCP data channels. In a third-party transfer, the initiator monitors or aborts the operation via the control channel, while data transfer is performed over one or more data channels between source and destination sites.

The `globus_ftp_client_library` implements the GridFTP client API. This API provides higher-level client features on top of the `globus_ftp_control` library, including complete file get and put operations, calls to set the level of parallelism for parallel data transfers, partial file transfer operations, third-party transfers, and eventually, functions to set TCP buffer sizes.

GRIDFTP PERFORMANCE

Preliminary performance measurements of our GridFTP prototype demonstrate that we can indeed obtain high performance and reliable transfers in wide area networks. Further improvements are expected as a result of tuning and improvements to the implementation.

Figure [1] shows the performance of GridFTP transfers between two workstations. Both workstations run the Linux operating system and have RAID storage systems with read/write bandwidth of approximately 60 megabytes per second. Gigabit Ethernet is the slowest link in the network path. The bottom curve in the graph shows GridFTP performance as the number of simultaneous TCP streams increases. For comparison, the top curve in the graph shows the performance of the same number of TCP streams measured by `iperf`, a tool for evaluating network performance that performs no disk I/O and has minimal CPU or protocol overhead [7]. `Iperf` provides one measurement of the maximum throughput of the network. Our experiment was run in random order relative to the number of streams, with the GridFTP measurement for a certain number of streams followed immediately by the `iperf` measurement for the same number of streams. For example, we took GridFTP measurements followed by `iperf` measurements for 18 simultaneous streams, then we took the two measurements for five simultaneous streams, etc. This randomization prevents any system or network trends from biasing the results, but assures that `iperf` and GridFTP measurements for the same number of streams are run close together temporally to reflect possible interactions with the number of streams. Each data point on the graph represents a single measurement. `Iperf` measurements were made using a one megabyte window size and ran for 30 seconds. GridFTP measurements recorded the time to transfer a one gigabyte file.

The graph shows that GridFTP bandwidth increases with the number of parallel TCP streams between the two workstations, until bandwidth reaches about 200 megabits per second with seven to ten TCP streams. Differences between `iperf` and GridFTP performance can be attributed to overheads including authentication and protocol operations, reporting performance to the client, and checkpointing data to allow restart. GridFTP achieves on average approximately 78% of the `iperf` bandwidth, although there is a great deal of

variability. We speculate that this variability is due to the requirement that GridFTP wait for any packets that are misrouted or dropped, while iperf simply runs for its allotted time and stops regardless of whether there are outstanding packets.

Figure 1: GridFTP performance compared to iperf measurements of network connection between Argonne National Laboratory and Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory.

Figure 2 demonstrates GridFTP reliability. We show aggregate parallel bandwidth for a period of approximately fourteen hours during the SC'00 Conference in Dallas, Texas, on November 7, 2000. This data corresponds to parallel transfers between two uniprocessor hosts using varying levels of parallelism, up to a maximum of eight streams. The graph was produced with the NetLogger system [8]. Bandwidth between the two hosts reaches approximately 80 megabits per second, somewhat lower than shown for the hosts in Figure 2, most likely due to disk bandwidth limitations. Figure 3 shows drops in performance due to various network problems, including a power failure for the SC network (SCiNet), DNS problems, and backbone problems on the exhibition floor. Because the GridFTP protocol supports restart of failed transfers, the interrupted transfers are able to continue as soon as the network is restored. Toward the right side of the graph, we see several temporary increases in aggregate bandwidth, due to increased levels of parallelism. The frequent drop in bandwidth to relatively low levels occurs because our current implementation of GridFTP destroys and rebuilds its TCP connections between consecutive transfers. To address this problem, our next GridFTP implementation will support data channel caching. This mechanism allows a

client to indicate that a TCP stream is likely to be re-used soon after the existing transfer is complete. In response to this hint, we will temporarily keep the TCP channel active and allow subsequent transfers to use the channel without requiring costly breakdown, restart, and re-authentication operations.

Figure 2: Bandwidth measured for a series of transfers performed over a 14 hour period, between Dallas and Chicago

Figure 3 and Table 1 address our achievable peak performance. These data were obtained during the Network Challenge competition at SC'00 in November 2000. Our configuration for this competition consisted of eight Linux workstations on the SC'00 exhibition floor in Dallas, Texas, sending data across the wide area network to eight workstations (four Linux, four Solaris) at Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory in California. Figure 4 illustrates the configuration. We used striped transfers during this competition, with a 2-gigabyte file partitioned across the eight workstations on the exhibition floor. Each workstation actually had four copies of its file partition. On each server machine, a new transfer of a copy of the file partition was initiated after 25% of the previous transfer was complete. Each new transfer creates a new TCP stream. At any time, there are up to four simultaneous TCP streams transferring data from each server in the cluster of eight workstations, for a total of up to 32 simultaneous TCP streams. Our current lack of data channel caching means that there are often fewer than four simultaneous streams transferring data on each host.

Figure 3: Experimental configuration for Network Challenge competition at SC'00.

Table 1 summarizes the results of the Network Challenge competition entry. It achieved a peak transfer rate of 1.55 gigabits/second over an interval of 0.1 seconds. This striped configuration was able to transfer data at a peak rate of 1.03 gigabits/second over an interval of 5 seconds. Over the hour-long period of our competition entry, we sustained an average data rate of 512.9 megabits per second. This corresponded to a total data transfer during that hour of 230.8 gigabytes, or a quarter of a terabyte.

Table 1: Network Challenge configuration and performance results

Striped servers at source location	8
Striped servers at destination location	8
Maximum simultaneous TCP streams per server	4
Maximum simultaneous TCP streams overall	32
Peak transfer rate over 0.1 seconds	1.55 Gbits/sec
Peak transfer rate over 5 seconds	1.03 Gbits/sec
Sustained transfer rate over 1 hour	512.9 Mbits/sec
Total data transferred in 1 hour	230.8 Gbytes

CONCLUSIONS

We have argued that high-performance, distributed data-intensive applications require fundamental service: secure, reliable, efficient data transfer. This service can be used to build a range of higher-level capabilities, including reliable creation of a copy of a data collection at a new location, selection of the best replica for a data transfer operation based on performance, and automatic creation of new replicas in response to application demands.

We have presented our design and implementation of this service. The GridFTP protocol implements extensions to FTP that provide GSI security and parallel, striped, partial, and third-party transfers. Performance studies of both components provide promising results.

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